

COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE DAMAGE TOLERANCE OF THERMOSET AND THERMOPLASTIC GLASS FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This experimental study contributes to an enhanced understanding of damage mechanisms of woven glass fiber-reinforced laminates (GFRP) under transverse low-velocity impact (LVI) loading. As matrix properties are essential in case of out-of-plane loadings, two different matrix systems, a thermoset epoxy and a thermoplastic polyamide 66 matrix, were experimentally compared. To guarantee comparable test conditions, all specimens were manufactured with a quasi-isotropic (QI) [(+45/-45)/(0/90)]_{4s} laminate lay-up, by using the same glass fiber fabric and by applying the same conditioning state for each test series. The force-time characteristics show no significant damage threshold load (DTL) for all specimens, which indicates the inhibition of pronounced delaminations. Different shapes of the damaged area depending on the conditioning state can be found during backlight and ultrasonic analyses. These non-destructive investigations emphasize the high damage tolerance as comparatively compact damaged areas were identified for all specimens. Thereby, the undulated fiber architecture of the fabric contributes significantly to a minor crack propagation compared to non-crimp fabric laminates. By opposing dehumidified specimens of the two different matrix systems in detail, even a lower damage tolerance of the polyamide matrix specimens seems to take effect.

1 INTRODUCTION

In contrast to superior in-plane properties of fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP), the through-the-thickness material behavior is mainly limited by matrix properties. This leads to an enhanced susceptibility for impact loading perpendicular to the component surface. Unfortunately, LVI damages often remain undetected, since they mainly occur within the laminate. However, they can significantly reduce stiffness and strength of composite structures, especially under compression and shear stresses [1]. In contrast to FRP, metallic components plasticize on its surface under LVI loadings, which eases maintenance tasks. Consequently, an enhanced damage tolerant design for safety-critical composite parts is necessary.

In aviation industry, a robust design philosophy tolerates these barely visible impact damages (BVID) between two scheduled maintenance intervals [2]. They can arise during manufacture, operation or maintenance. By applying this inevitable damage tolerant procedure, composite parts have to sustain their design loads despite a pre-damaged state, resulting in high safety factors. In course of time, thermoset state-of-the-art composite materials provoke economic challenges due to energy-intensive storage, long cycle times and costly joining processes. Concerning increasing production rates and high cost pressure in aviation industry, new production and material approaches are available in research and development. One of them is thermoplastic composites for primary aircraft structures [3]. Apart from advantages like cost-effective storage, mass manufacturing, joining and recycling processes, thermoplastic fiber-reinforced composites seem to provide an enhanced impact damage tolerance compared to thermoset fiber-reinforced composites. However, opposing statements are found in literature [4-6]. Consequently, the same conservative damage tolerant design limits are applied, since they are generally classified as polymer matrix composites [7]. In the authors'

opinion, this results from a current lack of understanding of similarities and differences in damage morphology of thermoset and thermoplastic composites.

To evaluate the influence of the matrix system on the damage tolerance under LVI, a comparative experimental study on glass fiber-reinforced composite plates with a conventional thermoset and thermoplastic matrix at predefined conditioning states is presented.

2 SPECIMEN PREPARATION

To investigate the influence of the matrix system on the damage behavior, two groups of specimens were manufactured. A thermoset epoxy and a thermoplastic polyamide 66 matrix system were reinforced with the same glass fiber fabric. Since the polyamide matrix has a high water absorption capability and low glass transition temperature, specimens were pretreated by choosing three different conditioning states. State-of-the-art epoxy matrix composites are known for their much lower sensitivity to moisture and moderate temperature dependency compared to polyamide matrix composites. Thus, solely one conditioning state was applied as a reference for the thermoset specimens.

2.1 Materials and manufacture

The thermoset specimens were manufactured in a resin transfer molding (RTM) process, whereas the thermoplastic plates were produced in an autoclave process. In both cases, the same twill-weave glass fiber fabric of type HEXFORCE® 01202 1000 TF970 (HEXEL) with an area weight of 290 g/m² was stacked to obtain a symmetrical, quasi-isotropic laminate lay-up with 16 layers. As thermoset matrix material, an epoxy system of the infusion resin EPIKOTE™ RIMR 935 and a hardener of type EPIKOTE™ RIMH 936 (HEXION) were mixed with a weight ratio of 100:29 and processed. For the autoclave process a polyamide 66 film grade, ULTRAMID A34 (BASF SE), was used. Both groups of specimens were manufactured with a target fiber volume fraction of about 50 % and a target wall thickness of 3.5 mm. The specimen dimensions of 150 x 100 mm² were realized with a milling machine. The obtained wall thickness was measured at seven plate positions according to a combination of DIN ISO 18352 [8] and DIN EN 6038 [9].

2.1 Specimen pretreatment

Three different conditioning states prior to impact testing – dry, humid and hot/wet – were set for the moisture sensitive polyamide specimens, whereas the epoxy specimens were solely dried in a vacuum furnace. For time reasons, all specimens were conditioned at elevated temperatures until reaching mass equilibrium. Mass equilibrium was defined as a maximum mass deviation tolerance of 0.05 % within three consecutive measurements, whereas a time gap of at least 24 h between each measurement had to be respected. For the hot/wet conditioned specimens, the maximum mass deviation tolerance is defined at 0.1 % respectively. These conditioning states were maintained during impact testing.

This results in four test series with two matrix materials and three conditioning states. Essential laminate and conditioning properties are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Laminate properties of manufactured and pretreated specimens with a symmetrical, quasi-isotropic [(+45/-45)/(0/90)]_{4s} laminate lay-up.

	GF-EP		GF-PA66	
	dry (D)	dry (D)	humid (H)	hot/wet (HW)
Conditioning	dry (D)	dry (D)	humid (H)	hot/wet (HW)
Impact test cond.	23° C / 0 % RH	23° C / 0 % RH	23° C / 50 % RH	70° C / 95 % RH
No. of spec.	12	3	9	5
Thickness	3.52 ± 0.014 mm	3.48 ± 0.003 mm	3.48 ± 0.031 mm	3.49 ± 0.012 mm
Notation	GF-EP QI D	GF-PA66 QI D	GF-PA66 QI H	GF-PA66 QI HW

3 EXPERIMENTAL TEST SET-UP

All specimens were tested at the in-house developed drop tower of the INSTITUTE FOR COMPOSITE MATERIALS (IVW), cf. Figure 1. The test rig consists of a stiff frame with a guiding rail which directs a carriage used as impact mass. The carriage is fitted with a load cell for the impact force measurement as well as a spherical impactor. The speed of the carriage is determined by using a single point laser vibrometer. The plates are fixed in their edge region onto a frame plate, according to DIN EN 6038 via four toggle clamps. Before starting the test series, the clamping forces were determined by using pressure-indicating films.

Figure 1: a) Basic experimental set-up for LVI testing and b) applied test rig configuration.

To establish constant test settings, all specimens were impacted according to their previously configured conditioning state. Therefore, dry and humid specimens were directly tested after having been removed from the vacuum furnace or climate chamber respectively, and after having cooled them to room temperature. Since no climate chamber is available during impact testing, preliminary investigations with an infrared camera were performed for the handling of the hot/wet specimens. To maintain the best possible conditioning state during testing with a minimum of temperature and moisture loss, an additional pretreatment was necessary. After removing from the climate chamber, the moisture loss is minimized by packing the hot/wet specimens into low-density polyethylene (LDPE) pressure lock bags. Afterward, these specimens are shortly stored in a mobile convection oven at 80° C. The convection oven is filled with additional water bowls to reduce moisture loss and located next to the test rig. Finally, the handling time was optimized to establish a temperature of 70° C after removing, unpacking and clamping the plates into the test rig.

4 RESULTS

Overall 29 specimens were impacted at three different impact energies (9 J, 12 J, 20 J) and three different conditioning states (D, H, HW) according to DIN EN 6038 without performing residual strength tests.

4.1 Impact tests

All specimens are characterized by the absence of a significant DTL, which is typically observable for composites manufactured with unidirectional prepregs or non-crimp fabrics [10]. This specific damage onset point correlates with first severe damages within the structure (mostly delaminations). In general, the DTL is followed by a sudden load drop and a reduced structural stiffness due to internal damages [11, 12].

As shown in preliminary tests with GF-PA66 specimens, the maximum impact force linearly increases with the impact energy. Thereby, the moisture content plays a minor role compared to the influence of the specimens' temperature [13]. The effect of a linear increase of maximum impact force

with higher impact energies is also independent of the matrix material, cf. Figure 2. The force-time curves are nearly identical at constant impact energy. Both thermoset and thermoplastic specimens show comparable maximum impact forces, force increase and decrease rates, as well as impact durations.

Figure 2: Comparison of exemplary force-time curves as a function of the matrix material (EP, PA66) and the impact energy (9 J, 12 J, 20 J) for the dry conditioning state.

Only with higher impact energies, a minor load drop at about 4 kN can be stated for the GF-PA66 specimens. This discontinuity in the force-time behavior is much lower than supposed for a DTL. The force-time gradient does not significantly change afterward either. However, this effect will be discussed later during ultrasonic analyses.

4.2 Impactor indentation

Due to the dynamic impact event, a distinct imprint of the impactor is visible on the impacted side of the plate. In aviation industry, this indentation is often used to evaluate BVID during walk-around since a (minor) direct visibility is present. In course of relaxation processes of the composite material, it is recommended to perform indentation measurement not directly after the impact event since indentation decreases and, consequently, becomes less visible [14]. Hence, all indentation measurements were performed via white light profilometry exactly 48 hours after impact.

Results show a growth of impactor indentation with increasing impact energy. This effect was already shown depending on the specimen conditioning. A comparable remaining indentation was stated for dry and humid specimens, which was much smaller than for the hot/wet tested specimens [13]. Based on these findings, the matrix system is another important influencing factor for external damage visibility, cf. Figure 3. The thermoplastic polyamide matrix shows a better BVID behavior since the remaining impactor indentation is up to 50 % higher compared to the epoxy specimens for a dry conditioning state. It is assumed that the differences of impactor indentation between polyamide and epoxy specimens will be greater with increasing moisture content and increasing temperature.

4.3 Damage projection area

After impact testing and indentation measurement, non-destructive analyses were performed. Ultrasonic analyses were conducted by using the impulse-echo method in immersion technique with a single element transducer. In order to guarantee constant test conditions for all specimens, they were referenced to itself by using a ring-shaped surface as artificial defect glued on the backside of the plates. Knowing the exact area of the ring-shaped reference surface, the attenuation levels were individually set for each specimen. Expectedly, the attenuation levels just slightly differ as wall thicknesses, fiber material and architecture, as well as ultrasonic test configurations did not change. With this individual calibration method, damage projection areas of the plates were calculated and compared. Since the GFRP specimens are semi-translucent, backlight analyses were performed redundantly. Results are not presented within this paper since relevant findings were the same, as expected.

Figure 3: Comparison of remaining indentation 48 hours after impact in dependence of the matrix material (EP, PA66) and the impact energy (9 J, 12 J, 20 J) for dehumidified specimens. The number of tested specimens is given in the bars, error bars are indicated when applicable.

Generally, the scatter of damage projection areas for the same matrix material at constant conditioning state is low. Consequently, representative impact tests were conducted. With increasing impact energy, the damaged area linearly increases for each test series, cf. Figure 4. Referring to the conditioning of the polyamide specimens, larger damage projection areas are observed with reduced moisture content. Interestingly, elevated temperature and moisture content of the hot/wet specimens result in a benign damage behavior, since the damaged areas are the smallest for all specimens. Due to the lower material stiffness, the hot/wet specimens show a more significant global deflection. At the same time, the specimens have more time to react to the impact loading (longer impact duration), which prevents them from sudden large-scale damages. In contrast, the complete absence of moisture for dry thermoplastic specimens is more severe than for state-of-the-art epoxy matrix specimens. The result of larger damaged areas of dry polyamide specimens correlates with the slight oscillation of the force signal at higher impact energies as mentioned earlier. To summarize, the minor load drops of the thermoplastic specimens within Figure 1 indicate additional inner damages, presumably sizable matrix cracks, which are caused by a brittle material behavior in lack of any moisture.

Figure 4: Damage projection area as a function of the impact energy in dependence of the conditioning state of GF-PA66 and GF-EP specimens.

Ultrasonic and backlight analyses also reveal no differences in the shape of the damage projection areas as a function of the matrix material. Relatively small damaged areas are identified for all specimens. Since the matrix materials are fundamentally different, these small damaged areas are mainly ascribed to the fiber architecture of the fabric. Due to enhanced friction during impact between the highly undulated fibers, matrix cracks are hindered to propagate extensively along the plate's

planar direction. In this case, the matrix material plays a minor role in damage inhibition. In contrast, the shape of the damage projection area differs depending on the conditioning state. On the one hand, polyamide specimens with 0 % and 50 % moisture content show a compact circular shape, whereof the dry specimens display a larger damage projection area compared to the humid ones. On the other hand, the hot/wet specimens are characterized by an elongated damage propagation according to the orientation of the (+45/-45) layers. However, the overall damage projection area stays smaller, cf. Figure 5.

Figure 5: Comparison of shape and extend of the damage projection area for GF-PA66 specimens at an impact energy of 20 J in dependence of their conditioning state: C-scan of the auxiliary reflector signal.

9 CONCLUSIONS

Within this study, the influence of a thermoset epoxy and a thermoplastic polyamide 66 matrix system on the damage tolerance of endless GF reinforced plates under LVI was investigated by respecting defined conditioning states during impact testing. Thereby, the GF-EP specimens were used as a reference. The main results are:

- No DTL is observed for all specimens since the fiber fabric prevents extensive crack propagation and delamination. By using fiber fabrics as a reinforcing structure, the matrix system has no significant influence on the maximum impact force and the impact duration.
- The absence of stored humidity from moisture sensitive thermoplastic composites reduces their damage tolerance significantly since comparatively large damaged areas evoke. This brittle damage behavior is mostly typical for thermoset materials. As a result, the conditioning state should not be neglected for structural design. However, the BVID behavior is significantly improved for the polyamide matrix material caused by a higher visible indentation on the specimen surface.
- With respect to preliminary investigations of the polyamide specimens, an interdependency is identified. Assuming constant impact energy, local and global damage extent are inverse proportional to each other depending on the conditioning state: the higher the local damages (impactor indentation), the smaller the global damages (damage projection area), and vice versa. During load introduction into the plate, kinetic impact energy is transformed into heat and mechanical work to provoke a local plasticizing on the specimens' surface: the smaller the strength of the plasticizing zone, the larger the impactor indentation. This results in less remaining energy for the planar propagation of damages within the plate. A smaller damage projection area is the consequence.

These findings will be substantiated during future investigations. Thereby, further destructive and non-destructive methods, like CT or microsection analyses, will be applied. In addition, GF-EP specimens at normal climate will be investigated. Then, the influence of fiber architecture will be discussed in the course of experimental investigations on non-crimp fabrics.

REFERENCES

- [1] T.-W. Shyr, Y.-H. Pan: “*Impact resistance and damage characteristics of composite laminates*”, Composite Structures, vol. 62, 2003, pp. 193–203, doi: 10.1016/S0263-8223(03)00114-4
- [2] U. P. Breuer: “*Commercial Aircraft Composite Technology*”, 1st edition, Springer International Publishing Switzerland, 2016, ISBN: 978-3-319-31917-9
- [3] B.H.A.H. Tijs, C.S. Lopes, A. Turon, C. Bisagni, J. Waleson, J.W. van Ingen and S.L. Veldman: “*Virtual testing of thermoplastic composites: towards a hybrid simulation-physical testing pyramid*”, 18th European Conference on Composite Materials, Athens, 24th- 28th June 2018
- [4] B. Vieille, V. M. Casado and C. Bouvet: “*About the impact behavior of woven-ply carbon fiber-reinforced thermoplastic- and thermosetting-composites: A comparative study*”, Composite Structures, Elsevier, vol. 101, 2013, pp. 9-21, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2013.01.025>
- [5] H. Y. Nedzad, A. Auffray, C. T. McCarty and R. O’Higgins: “*Impact damage response of carbon fibre-reinforced aerospace composite panels*”, 20th International Conference on Composite Materials, Copenhagen, 19-24th July 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.compscitech.2008.11.031
- [6] N. Uda, K. Ono and K. Kunoo: “*Compression fatigue failure of CFRP laminates with impact damage*”, Composites Science and Technology, vol. 69, 2009, pp. 2308–2314, doi: 10.1016/j.compscitech.2008.11.031
- [7] S. R. Reid and G. Zhou: “*Impact behaviour of fibre-reinforced composite materials and structures*”, 1st edition, Woodhead Publishing Ltd, 2000, ISBN: 1 85573 423 0
- [8] DIN ISO 18352: „*Kohlenstofffaserverstärkte Kunststoffe – Ermittlung der Compression-After-Impact-Eigenschaften bei spezifischer Aufprallenergie*”, DIN-Normenausschuss Kunststoffe (FNK), 2017
- [9] DIN EN 6038: „*Prüfverfahren – Bestimmung der Restdruckfestigkeit nach Schlagbeanspruchung*“, DIN-Normenausschuss Luft- und Raumfahrt (NL), 2016
- [10] F. Schimmer, S. Ladewig, N. Motsch, J. Hausmann and I. Ehrlich: „*Comparison of low-velocity impact damage behavior of unidirectional carbon fiber-reinforced thermoset and thermoplastic composites*”, 22nd Symposium on Composites, Kaiserslautern, 26th - 28th June 2019 - to be published
- [11] S. Abrate: “*Impact Engineering of Composite Structures*”, CISM Courses and Lectures, vol. 526, Springer Wien NewYork, 2011, ISBN: 978-3-7091-0522-1
- [12] D.D.R. Cartié and P.E. Irving: “*Effect of resin and fibre properties on impact and compression after impact performance of CFRP*”, Composites: Part A, vol. 33, issue 4, pp. 483-493, Elsevier, 2001, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-835X\(01\)00141-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-835X(01)00141-5)
- [13] F. Schimmer, N. Motsch, J. Hausmann: „*Experimental investigations on the impact behavior of woven thermoplastic glass fiber-reinforced laminates*“, 18th European Conference on Composite Materials, Athens, 24th - 28th June 2018
- [14] C. Fualdes: “*Composites at Airbus: Damage tolerance methodology*”, FAA Workshop for composite damage tolerance and maintenance, Chicago, 19th – 21th Jul 2016